

A STUDY ON IMPACT OF COVID -19 AMONG STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Higher education establishments have been severely impacted by the disorderly fallout from the COVID-19 pandemic. This study aims to investigate the perceived impact of COVID-19 on student's learning and academic performance through a qualitative approach. This paper aims to analyse the impact that COVID-19 has had on different personal factors of students: (i) satisfaction with life; (ii) living condition (iii) depression, anxiety, and stress, as well as factors related to academic development; (iv) motivation and the creation of teaching and learning strategies in covid period; and (v) the impression of one's level of flexibility in the face of the novel circumstances introduced by the university system. The study discusses the impact of COVID-19 on students learning, living condition and mental health. This study collected the data both primary and secondary among college students and the study tries to suggest some of the measures to improve the condition of students from impact of COVID-19.

Keywords: learning strategies, living condition, degree of adaptability

INTRODUCTION

Up until June 2021, there were over 170 million COVID-19 infections worldwide, and the illness claimed over 3.5 million lives. For those whose loved ones have passed away and those who suffer lifelong sequelae, the consequences of the pandemic are forever irreversible. Statistically, the mortality rate caused by SARS-CoV2 is not as high as that of many other viruses. Its potential for spread, with a reproduction number R_0 ranging from 3.5 to 6.4, poses a threat, nevertheless. Put differently, the horrifying infectivity of the disease is demonstrated by the fact that, in the absence of immunization, one infected individual can infect 3.5 to 6.4 other persons. COVID-19 caused a pandemic that spread swiftly and changed people's lives. Humans evolved from a highly social species to one that is more akin to the "caveman" lifestyle, consuming more food and fat and being less active. Wearing mask in public and social distancing has kept people away from the transitional space in the development of human relationships. Here, the phrase "cave" also refers to a virtual environment into which we frequently descend and get cut off from society.

Economically, changes in human behaviours' lead to changes in the long-run consumption structure. Online services will increase and offline services will decrease as more people come out of the cave and access the internet. The gap between the rich and the poor widens as a result of the developments. The social

repercussions would be a rise in crime, a fall in the rate of required schooling, a decrease in life expectancy, and an increase in the demand for medical attention.

This microscopic parasite got into people's lives in such a way that it caused thousands of fatalities worldwide. Even though there have been previous pandemics in the era of science, technology, and social media, when knowledge spreads faster than sound, this one caught everyone's attention. Its effects are so severe that, a year later, the circumstances remain the same and are now at their worst. Similar to last year, pupils' school lives have been completely destroyed. Exam cancellations have been declared in numerous states, including the boards, or the exam has been postponed for an unspecified period of time. We all know the pandemic affects life as a student and increased also workload. The effects of COVID-19 have had a total impact on the education system. In an urgent attempt to save time, schools, colleges, and institutions have closed, exams have been postponed, and online courses have begun. This has a negative impact on students' personal and academic lives. Almost 1.6 billion pupils were impacted by the global school closures caused by the COVID-19 epidemic (UNESCO 2020). A child's learning can suffer greatly and for a long time from even brief disruptions in their education. Education systems have varied, albeit uneven, capacities to address the problem by providing children and families with remote learning and support.

Globally, the COVID-19 pandemic has an impact on every facet of human activity, including science, education, research, sports, entertainment, transportation, worship, social gathering/interactions, economy, businesses, and politics. The truth of the situation was difficult to accept, and the education sector continues to be among the most severely affected by the coronavirus pandemic. In fact, the entire world was in turmoil due to the COVID-19 dangers. Thus, the issues and their effects on pupils during COVID-19 are discussed in the current study.

Overview of Coronavirus Disease

Coronavirus Disease is a contagious disease that first emerged in Wuhan, China in 2019. The World Health Organization later designated it as "COVID-19," which stands for Coronavirus Disease 2019. For decades, the coronavirus outbreak has been among the worst worldwide pandemics. The increase in mortality was distressing, as was the ease of transmission. According to research, the risk of developing serious illnesses from coronavirus was higher in older adults and those with underlying medical conditions such as diabetes, cancer, chronic respiratory disorders, and cardiovascular diseases (W.H.O., 2020).

The coronavirus can cause a sore throat, runny nose, persistent coughing or sneezing, difficulty breathing, and exhaustion. Improved personal hygiene, such as frequent hand washing with alcohol-based sanitizers, a good respiratory attitude (close coughing and sneezing), and other personal protection techniques like wearing face masks, social distancing, refraining from touching your face, and limiting social interactions by staying home alone or avoiding unnecessary trips or gatherings are some of the suggested measures to stop the coronavirus pandemic. In order to properly manage the outbreak and address its aftereffects, coronavirus is a worldwide issue that calls for increased action coordination and international

cooperation. As a result, the UN made a request for \$2 billion to help with international efforts to combat the coronavirus pandemic. If people disregard or fail to strictly go by public health recommendations and regulations, the repercussions of COVID-19 may be more severe.

Impact of Coronavirus Pandemic on Education

Globally, the coronavirus outbreak had a detrimental impact on educational endeavours. Worldwide school closures resulted from the coronavirus pandemic's impact on educational systems (Wikipedia, 2020b). It created serious disruptions in academic activities, as well as in career plans. Many nations shuttered their schools in an effort to contain the coronavirus epidemic as part of the worldwide response to tackle COVID-19. Over 100 countries adopted national closures, affecting more than half of the world's student population, according to monitoring conducted by the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2020a).

According to ABC News (2020), even Prime Minister Boris Johnson of Britain, who had previously opposed the plan, subsequently acknowledged that "closing down schools could place further downward pressure on the upward curve of the Coronavirus outbreak." Nigeria, Ghana, Senegal, South Africa, China, Kazakhstan, Ethiopia, Honduras, India, Japan, Iran, USA, France, Spain, Italy, North and South Korea, Lebanon, Vietnam, Thailand, Germany, and South Korea are just a few of the nations who stopped their schools as a result of COVID-19. Closing schools has a negative impact on people in all communities due to its significant social, educational, and financial consequences; however, underprivileged individuals and their families are disproportionately affected (UNESCO, 2020b). Should the disease persist in spreading and a more dependable coronavirus treatment not be discovered in a timely manner, the disruption that COVID-19 has caused in the educational sector might endure longer than anticipated. "The global scale and speed of the educational disruption due to coronavirus is unparalleled and, if prolonged, could threaten the right to education," stated UNESCO Director-General Audrey Azoulay, as quoted by VOA News (2020). Unplanned school closures can undoubtedly lead to serious issues for parents, teachers, students, and society at large. Students' academic performance and interest may suffer as a result. Inactivity among pupils has the potential to cause kids to become involved in criminal activities, lose interest in studying, and perform poorly academically. Concerns over the effects of closing schools were also voiced by the US Centres for Disease Prevention and Control (CDC). "Longer closures may result in more students congregating outside of schools," the CDC warns.

According to Quentin (2014), closing schools is a contentious issue that can affect a sizable portion of the student body in the receiving schools. Academic progress and the quality of teaching and learning can be impacted, especially for students with special needs or learning disabilities who frequently need more hands-on support and direction from their teachers. Technology can be helpful in mitigating some of the negative consequences of school closures, but it cannot replace the important in-person interactions that take place between students and teachers. Additionally, it is more difficult to fully utilize the benefits of learning

technology while schools are closed since a large number of pupils lack access to the required supportive technologies. Even though, against all odds, mathematical models and empirical analysis of reactive school closures in previous pandemics indicates that it reduces the total number of cases in the community by 25% and delays the peak of the pandemic by a week or two, proactive school closures during pandemics remain one of the most effective interventions that can be used to lessen the impact of epidemic disease (Erika and Nicholas, 2020).

Effect of closure of educational institution among students

According to UNESCO (2020b), some of the harmful effects of closure of educational institution for coronavirus are as follows:

1. Interrupted learning: educational institution provides essential learning and when they are closed, students are deprived of opportunities for growth and development.
2. Increased pressure on students: lack of proper guidance
3. Social Isolation: Considering the fact that educational institutions are hubs for social activity and human interactions, school closures can deprive youth and children of some social communications and socializations that are essential to learning, development and creativity.
4. The closure of educational institutions due to COVID-19 lockdown had a negative impact on the overall subjective wellbeing of adolescents and youth in India, especially those from disadvantaged backgrounds. They reported higher levels of sadness, boredom, loneliness, and anxiety during the pandemic
5. The COVID-19 pandemic has exposed the many inadequacies and inequities in our education systems, such as the lack of access to digital learning resources, the supportive environments, and the alignment between resources and needs. The loss of instructional time delivered in a school setting could lead to lower skills and lower GDP in the long run.
6. The COVID-19 pandemic has also affected the student equity and inclusion, as the most vulnerable students faced additional barriers to access and benefit from education. These include students from low-income and single-parent families, immigrant, refugee, ethnic minority and Indigenous backgrounds, with diverse gender identities and sexual orientations, and those with special education needs.
7. The COVID-19-related school closures also had an effect on student achievement and motivation in Canada. The study found that students experienced a decline in both academic achievement and motivation during the first wave of school closures in 2020. Moreover, the socioeconomic achievement gap increased by up to 30%.

8. The COVID-19 pandemic has also left a lasting impact on the education of an entire generation. This resulted in learning loss, increased dropout rates, reduced social interaction, and mental health issues.

Impact of COVID-19:

COVID-19 has had a significant impact on students all over the world, affecting their academic, personal, and professional lives. Some of the impacts are:

- **Mental health:** Many students have experienced increased levels of anxiety, depression, stress, and loneliness due to the pandemic. They have faced challenges such as isolation, uncertainty, disruption of routines, loss of social support, and fear of infection. Some students have also suffered from grief, trauma, or abuse during this time. These psychological impacts can affect their academic performance, motivation, and well-being.
- **Educational outcomes:** The pandemic has also disrupted the educational process for many students, forcing them to adapt to online learning, reduced interaction with teachers and peers, and limited access to resources and facilities. Some students have faced difficulties in accessing reliable internet, devices, or software for online learning. Others have struggled with managing their time, staying focused, or coping with distractions at home. Some students have also had to balance their studies with other responsibilities such as work, family, or caregiving. These factors can affect their learning outcomes, engagement, and satisfaction.
- **Career prospects:** The pandemic has also affected the career prospects of many students, especially those who are graduating or seeking employment. They have faced challenges such as reduced job opportunities, delayed or cancelled internships, lower wages, and increased competition. Some students have also had to change their career plans or goals due to the changing demands and expectations of the labour market. These impacts can affect their employability, income, and career development

Statement of problem

The various negative and positive Impact of deadly corona virus .so, the present study describes the covid-19 impact among students in the study area.

Objectives of the study

- To examine the impact of COVID-19 on student education.
- To investigate the various challenges that hinder continued/online education during the COVID-19 lockdown period.

Need for the study

The study of the impact of COVID-19 among students is important because the pandemic has significantly changed the education system and student behaviour and affected the learning outcomes also well-being of millions of students around the world. So the present study need to research on impact of COVID-19 among the students.

Review of literature:

The Impact of COVID-19 on Student Experiences and Expectations (2020) by Esteban M. Aucejo: In his paper reported that about 1,500 students at a large public university in the US, using an instrument designed to recover the causal impact of the pandemic on students' current and expected outcomes. The study also shows that COVID-19 has large negative effects on students' academic performance, graduation plans, employment prospects, and future earnings. It also reveals that these effects are highly heterogeneous and often follow existing socioeconomic divides.

Student Resilience and COVID-19: A Review of the Literature (2020) by Mitzi s Brammer: In his paper reveals that resilience as the ability to adapt and cope with adversity and stress, and discusses the factors that influence student resilience, such as personal characteristics, social support, coping strategies, and institutional policies. This study also provides some recommendations for enhancing student's resilience during and after the pandemic.

The Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Education System in Developing Countries_(2020) by Seble Tadesse: In his work, he examines the impact of COVID-19 on the education system in developing countries, focusing on the challenges and opportunities of online learning. This study finds out the impacts of COVID-19 on children, students, teachers, and parents, and the recommended solutions for ensuring the continuity and quality of education during the pandemic. This research also explores the potential innovations and transformations that COVID-19 can bring to education in developing country.

A Comprehensive Study on COVID-19 Pandemic: An Impact on School Education in India (2020) by Ms. Toshika Pareek and Dr.Kiran Soni: have conducted an empirical study on the impact of COVID-19 on school education in India, based on a literature review and a survey of parents, teachers, and students. It's find out the concept and importance of online education, the challenges and benefits of online learning, and the expectations and satisfaction of stakeholders regarding online education. They also suggest some measures for improving online education in India.

Area of study

This study was conducted in Dr. Ambedkar law university students, Taramani, Chennai. Study area has selected only 2nd year BA course in Law University. This course has totally 150 students. Among 150 students the researcher has selected randomly 53 students only in the study area.

Methodology

The present has been adopted descriptive method. This study aimed at examining the impact of COVID-19 among students.

Data collection

Interview schedule, Google form and observation tool used for the data collection and direct interview was conducted in the research area because it adds more valid points from the respondents.

Sources of Data

Primary sources: Interview, observation and google questionnaire.

Secondary sources: Published reports and articles.

Scope and Limitation of the study

- The study is done on the basis of the data provided by the respondents which may affect the study if the data provided by them turns out to be wrong.
- The study is conducted on a small fraction of people whose results may not be generalised in the entire population.
- The questionnaire is based on our research objectives.
- The study was conducted only in BA.LLB students. So the future researcher has been conducting more research in this area through identification of the research gap.

Data analysis and interpretation

Comfortableness of students

Out of 53 students selected for the study, 54.7 percentages of them stated feeling comfortable in educational institutions and 45.3 percentages of them reported that not feeling comfortable.

It concludes that more number of study respondents is feeling comfortable in educational institutions in the study area. so the covid-19 gave the great draw back for educational systems and on the others side more online and technological education was developed during that period.

Feeling of isolation

Total respondent selected for the study, 73.1 percentages of students feel isolated during online class followed by 26.9 percentages of students doesn't feel isolated during the COVID-19 period.

It is clear that majority of the study area respondents are hailing isolation in the COVID period.

Satisfaction level of the students

Among the respondents it has been seen that 65.4 Percentage of them reported that get moderate level of satisfaction in education followed by 30.8 Percentage of them stated that get less level of satisfaction in online education and remaining 3.8% percentage of them get high level of satisfaction from online learning.

More number of respondents is stated their attained satisfaction from moderate online education and only 3.8 percentages of them stated high level of satisfaction from online learning in the study area.

Accessibility of Technology

It has been found that 71.7 Percentage of them think that every student's did not get access to technology followed by 22.6 Percentage think they may get access to technology and only 5.7 Percentage think that everybody got access to technology.

It's found to be majority of the study respondents reported that every student's did not get access to technology for online education in the study area.

Impact on student's health

71.7 Percentage of respondents stated of them think that their health gets affected followed by 20.8 Percentage are not sure of their impact and only 7.5 Percentage think their health does not get affected.

Here, Majority of the respondents reported that during the COVID-19 Period online education affect the health in the study area. Because of them continuously sitting in a particular place and seeing mobile phones.

Interest of students towards studies

69.8 Percentage of them stated negatively which means that interest will be reduced in online education followed by 24.5 Percentage are not sure and only 5.7 Percentage of them stated positive way that means interest doesn't reduce towards studies among the students in the study area.

More number of respondents has stated that the learning interest will be reduced because of online education.

Efficiency of online learning

90.6percent of them stated that efficiency of online education is very less and only 9.4 per cent of the respondents stated that is very efficiency.

Majority of respondents feel that online class is not efficient and only 9.4 Percentage feel it's efficient in the study area.

Major findings

- The present study find out most of the respondents feel uncomfortable in studying at home comparing to coming to college.
- The research found that majority of the respondent feel isolated during online class.
- The study shows more number of respondent feel less satisfied with online teaching concept in the study area.
- It is clear that most of the respondent feel that every student's did not get access to technology during lock down period in the study area.
- It is found to be majority of respondents felt their health gets affected during online class; they have been suffering from various mental disorders such as depression, anxiety and stress etc.
- The study indicated most of the respondents of them stated reduced their interest towards their learning in the period of COVID- 19.
- It has been found that learning efficiency has been reduced in online learning comparing to classroom learning in the study area.

Suggestions

Some possible suggestions for reducing the impact of COVID-19 are given below

- Reducing the non-availability of technology. GO's and NGO's needs to address the beneficiary of technology users and providing appropriate and affordable technological facilities to the unreached people.
- Create new and entertaining productive education for online learning.
- To provide periodical interval and create more interest to the online learning among the students in the study area.
- Keep on monitoring and evaluate how the pandemic has affected the academic performance, mental health, and future prospects of students from different backgrounds, regions, and levels of education in COVID-19 in the study area.
- Comparing and contrasting the different strategies and policies adopted by various students' capability and well-being of students learning for online education in the study area.
- Evaluate the effectiveness and challenges of online learning as a response to COVID-19 impact, and suggest ways to improve its accessibility, quality, and engagement for students and teachers.
- Find out the potential long-term consequences of COVID-19 impact on students', improve learning interest, skills development based on their career choices and learning outcomes, and take up proper solution to address the non -availability of technology and affordability of technological / online learning and also need to identify students lag in the learning process and that will be sort out in the study area.
- Increasing the role of parents, peers, and communities in supporting students during the pandemic, and identify best practices and recommendations for enhancing students' learning and skill of patience listening among the students in the study area.
- To concentrate on students health as well as learning process.

Conclusion

Students are very important for a nation, as they are the future citizens who will contribute to its development and prosperity. Students can play various roles in nation-building, such as:

- Learning and acquiring knowledge and skills that will help them to become productive and responsible members of society.
- Participating in social, cultural, and political activities that will enhance their civic awareness and engagement.
- Innovating and creating new solutions and ideas that will address the challenges and opportunities facing the nation and the world.

- Educating and inspiring others, especially the younger generations, to follow their example and pursue their dreams.

The benefits of education for students and the nation are immense. Education can improve health and livelihoods, reduce poverty and inequality, promote social stability and peace, and drive economic growth. Education can also empower students to become agents of change and leaders of tomorrow.

Therefore, it is essential that students are given the opportunity and support to fulfil their potential and role in nation-building. This requires providing them with quality education that is accessible, inclusive, relevant, and equitable. It also requires encouraging them to develop their talents, passions, and values, and to use them for the common good. Therefore, it is essential to improve the conditions of students from the great impact of COVID -19.

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